

Behavioral variation in private zoo of wild captive animals-a review

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ABSTRACT

Animals become endanger and extinct due to fragmentation, a population increase of humans, and habitat loss. So, for the safety of these animals, they brought into captivity. But in captivity, their behavior becomes changes due to a different environment than in wild. But zoos are the place which is used for research and recreational purposes. Behaviors further divided into abnormal and general behaviors and interactions with one another and with other animals. For the better study of animal behavior first, we know the life history of the animals and cooperate with zoo management authorities for better conservation of animals in captivity.

Keywords: Zoo, Animal, Behavior, Monkey

INTRODUCTION

Zoos or parks are the places where wild animals live in captivity for the visitor's entertainment, recreational and educational determinations (Nemat *et al.*, 2015; Aloysius *et al.*, 2020; Khan *et al.*, 2020). The zoological garden is used for the welfare, protection, and preservation of wild animals from environmental hazardous and other disasters (Ahmad *et al.*, 2015). Behaviors are observed for the information and welfare of animals (Moreno *et al.*, 2007). But due to captivity mostly animal's life becomes disturbed and they perform a lot of abnormal behaviors (Bacon, 2018; Falk, 2009; Packer, 2006). The behavioral change in captivity occurs on 3 levels. 1st the animal changes its behavior immediately to meet its needs properly (Darwin, 2010; Bolhuis and Giraldeau, 2004). 2nd the life in captivity is difficult as compared to the wild because of restriction and animals prepare themselves for the future (Price, 1970; van der Jeugd and Prins, 2000). 3rd they adapt many behaviors for their survivorship and transmitted generation after generation such as bear the loud noise. But mostly abnormal behavior develops (Mench, 1998).

ZOO VALUES

By forming a children's zoo, it is very pleasant for children to get awareness about the captive animals, their conservation, and perceive the wild animals of other countries (Ballantyne and Packer, 2016; Canino *et al.*, 2010). Modern wildlife refuges have so many responsibilities for the maintenance of their work in which scientific research, preservation, regeneration, and education are involved to achieve all this, they have some aims, objectives, and ideas to make their centers fascinating for the public and allow students for gaining education (Roe *et al.*, 2014; Rose *et al.*, 2019). But this captive environment is also affected negatively on animal's behavior (Lowe, 2013; Hancocks, 2001; Kisling, 2000).

BEHAVIORAL VARIATION IN DIFFERENT CAPTIVE ANIMALS

The life of animals in captivity is completely different as compared to the wild, social interaction, space, feeding, diet, human presence, and climate everything different from the wild.

They cannot select their environment and face many challenges. They spend easy life in captivity for their survival (Powell and Bullock, 2014). If captivity does not suit the animals and if not properly handle the animals it may cause a lot of diseases and unnatural stress, physical diseases, and abnormal behaviors in animals (Nowak *et al.*, 1999). In these abnormal behaviors, repetitive and non-functional behaviors include in which swaying, head bobbing, bar-biting, over-grooming, licking, and pacing (Bacon, 2018; Falk, 2009; Packer, 2006).

EXAMPLES OF BEHAVIORAL STUDY IN CAPTIVE ANIMALS

Pacing and Circling

Animals move back and forth or in a circle in one manner and on same pathway. Some animals show this behavior like big cats and wolves (Mason, 2006; Earnhardt, 2001).

Coprophilia and Coprophagia

The captive primates smearing the edibles and feces on the glass of the enclosure (Mason, 1991; Fazal *et al.*, 2014; Fischbacher *et al.*, 1999; Montaudouin *et al.*, 2004).

Over-grooming and Self-Mutilation

The animals physically harm themselves by hitting head on wall, biting on their tail and body and pulling their body fur (Ricker *et al.*, 1987). The animals show this behavior are apes, bear, big cats and giraffe (Mason *et al.*, 2004; Young *et al.*, 2010).

Vomiting and Regurgitation

In captivity, due to food change some animals stomach become disturbed and cause vomiting and regurgitation like in primates and apes (Mason, 1993; Vickery and Mason, 2005).

Bar-biting and Tongue-playing

Giraffe and other primates licking, biting and sucking the fence and captivity walls (Seeber *et al.*, 2012; Tarouet *et al.*, 2007; Tetley *et al.*, 2012; Shyne, 2006).

Head-bobbing, Swaying and Weaving

Bear and Elephants move their heads up and down or back and forth and also swaying their whole body (Ricker *et al.*, 1987; Razal *et al.*, 2017; Reinhardt *et al.*, 1981).

Neck-Twisting

In which animals like giraffe, llama, bear and primate twist and roll their neck or bend neck backward (Ames, 1993, Phillips *et al.*, 2003, Pratt *et al.*, 1982).

Rocking

In apes, they hang their legs and move backward and forward (Lutz *et al.*, 2003).

Figure 1 This chart indicates the Behavioral variation in Captive animals that which behavior mostly present in captive animals (O'REGAN, 2005)

Table 1: Ethogram of Behavioral study of captive animals (Razal *et al.*, 2017).

Animals	Behavioral study of wild captive animals
Giraffe	Pacing, body rocking, hair and feature picking, tongue rolling and licking inedible objects (Bashaw <i>et al.</i> , 2001).
Monkey	Self- suckling, oral stereotypy (tongue movement and tongue chew) repetitively clings on genitals, repetitively moved from one posture to another like biped to crocodiles postures, continually moving their head, move their head up and down, swing themselves repeatedly from left to right, perform pacing and flipping stereotype behaviors, repetitively bite on the tail, lick on the tail and the other parts of the body, lick and gnaws the bars and repeatedly manipulate the collar, feeding tray and other objects (Würbel, 2006, Amo <i>et al.</i> , 2006, Andersen <i>et al.</i> , 2006).
Apes	Swinging, flipping, bouncing, rocking and pacing, self-grasping, hair pulling, nail sucking, and eye-poking include self-directed movements (Anderson <i>et al.</i> , 2016, Appleby <i>et al.</i> , 1987, Asa <i>et al.</i> , 2001).
Puma	Walking, running and jumping, inactivity like sleeping, lying, standing and sitting, urination, eating, licking themselves and other members, rubbing their claws with objects, show teeth and claws one puma to other, release sound from the mouth, stared and attack toward visitors (Asner <i>et al.</i> , 2009, Bachmann <i>et al.</i> , 2003, Basu <i>et al.</i> , 2019).
Wolves	Pacing and jumping, in captivity also increased the aggressive behavior in wolves (Mason, 2006, Bauer <i>et al.</i> , 2013).
Lions	Aggression, pawing, rushing, and chasing (Burger <i>et al.</i> , 1993).

Tiger	Pacing, auto-playing or rolling, rocking, licking, head bobbing, or walking in circles (Sheperdesonet <i>et al.</i> , 1999, Bauer <i>et al.</i> , 2016).
Brown bear	Counting verbal, head, and locomotory related behaviors, and pacing are the foremost commonly seen (Mason <i>et al.</i> , 2004).
Zebra	Zebras in zoos spend most of their time bolstering, and the larger part of the rest of the time they spend lying, strolling, and alarm.
Deer	Disgorging, chewing, and gulping (Yang <i>et al.</i> , 2003).
Rhinoceros	Pacing and circling (Wolfensohn <i>et al.</i> , 2018, Bauman <i>et al.</i> , 2008).
Elephant	The elephant keepers call these stereotypical movements “weaving”
Hippopotamus	Pacing and stress(Whitehead, 1997, Bercovitch <i>et al.</i> , 2010).
Horse	Licking the environment, lip-licking, pretense chewing or teeth pounding, self-biting, and rubbing self, as well as movement stereotypes, counting pawing, tail swishing, entryway kicking or box kicking, and head tossing/nodding (Weatherall, 2006).
Pig	Changes of behavior of pigs display leadership of the cultivate and to propose measures for killing the causes of changes within the behavior of pigs (Watters, 2014, Berger, 1993, Bostock, 1993).

WELFARE OF ANIMALS

The welfare of animals is very important for reducing the animal’s abnormal behavior, stress, and successful reproduction (Bacon, 2018, Boyd, 1991, Bradfield, 2005). Zoos are sustaining a high standard animal welfare organization which is important for proper and governmental reasons (Wolfensohn *et al.*, 2018, Broom, 1983, Brown, 2013). Before forming any welfare program, it is important to know the animal's biological status, environmental conditions in which animals survive in captivity, and history (Wolfensohn *et al.*, 2018, Camus *et al.*, 2013, Canino, 2010). The welfare of animals is also important because of a steady and healthy population and the reproduction of animals (Stevens *et al.*, 2005, De Roucket *et al.*, 2005). Human used animal parts viz. bone (Ijaz and Iftikhar, 2021), eggs (Tariq, 2020), fat (Noor and Haider, 2020; Ijaz and Faiz, 2021; Saleem *et al.*, 2021), feathers (Adil and Tariq, 2020), honey (Umair and Yaqoob, 2018; Altaf and Umair, 2020), meat (Haidar and Bashir, 2021), milk (Aslam and Faiz, 2020), and skin (Zainab, 2021) for export (Altaf *et al.*, 2017), food (Tariq, 2020), magic, medicine (Muhammad *et al.*, 2017; Mughal *et al.*, 2020; Abbasi, 2021; Altaf *et al.*, 2021; Ijaz and Iftikhar, 2021; Saleem *et al.*, 2021; Zainab, 2021), narratives (Altaf *et al.*, 2017), superstitious (Altaf *et al.*, 2020), and trade from the origin of human. Human contact with fauna may lead to zoonotic diseases (Altaf, 2020).

CONCLUSION

It is difficult to compare the observed behavior with the different observed behavioral events, that’s why the interactions and behavioral activities do not compare so, without any disturbance it is studied on large scale (Darwin, 2010, Deacon *et al.*, 2018). It is difficult to know the real intension of animals so, we can only observe by visualization (Clubb *et al.*, 2013, Del Castillo *et al.*, 2005, Mahenya *et al.*, 2016, Marriner *et al.*, 1994). For long-distance connections, we also use odorous signals which remain unpredictable (Kingdon, 1997, Conte, 2014). The best method to study the giraffe behavior is to first understand the life history of the giraffe rather it is present in the wild or in captivity (Hopcraft *et al.*, 2005). For a better understanding of animal behavior,

we should help the conservation department for the improvement of animal conservation in captivity and the wild by creating management plans (Coe, 1967, Cozzi *et al.*, 2012).

Figure 4: This chart indicates the percentage % behavioral variation of captive animals (Altman, 1998, Crawley *et al.*, 1997).

Figure 3 This chart indicates the ranking of animals according to their endanger, conservation and visitor's preference status (Würbel, 2006, De Waal *et al.*, 2009)

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